

Thallium(III) Acetate Oxidation of some Substituted-4-piperidones : A Kinetic and Mechanistic Study

(Mrs.) KR. MEENAL* and (Mrs.) S. LALITHA

Department of Chemistry, Seethalakshmi Ramaswamy College (Autonomous), Trichy-620 002

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Kinetics of oxidation of 2,6 diphenyl-4-piperidone, 3-alkyl and 3,5-dimethyl substituted 4 piperidones with Tl^{III} in aqueous acetic acid (80 v, v) in the presence of sulphuric acid (0.75 mol dm^{-3}) at constant ionic strength ($\mu=2.25 M$) over the temperature range 30–55° have been investigated. The reactions obey second order kinetics. Dependence on acidity is unity. Added sodium sulphate does not have any effect. Activation parameters have been calculated and the structure-reactivity relationships discussed. A mechanism involving fast enolisation step is postulated.

Despite a wide spectrum of kinetics and mechanism of Tl^{III} oxidation of ketones available in the literature^{1,2} heterocyclic ketones are left out to be explored. The strikingly stable nature of Tl^{III} with the inert pair effect, the moderately high redox potential (1.25 V) of $Tl^{III} - Tl^I$ system and the ability to form organometallic derivative make Tl^{III} a versatile oxidising agent. We have, therefore, undertaken the title investigation with the view to attain a better understanding of the mechanism and conformational effect on the Tl^{III} oxidation rates of variously substituted six-membered heterocyclic ketones.

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of a series of substituted 4-piperidones by Tl^{III} have been carried out in aqueous acetic acid at constant acidity and ionic strength under pseudo-first order conditions. The reaction is practically negligible in the absence of added mineral acid, sulphuric acid and is conveniently carried out by maintaining required concentration of sulphuric acid. The second order rate constants determined were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$ error. The oxidation of 3-methyl-2,6-diphenyl-4-piperidone has been studied in greater detail.

The second order rate constants for oxidation of 3-methyl by Tl^{III} are given in Table 1. Variation of either [3-methyl] or $[Tl^{III}]$ has no appreciable effect on the rate constants, indicating that the reaction follows second order—first order each in 3-methyl and Tl^{III} . The rate of oxidation is not affected by change in ionic strength by adding required amounts of sodium sulphate at constant $[H^+]$ indicating that the reaction is between an ion and a dipole molecule.

As mentioned earlier, the oxidation of 3-methyl by Tl^{III} is negligible in the absence of added mineral acid and increases with increase in $[H^+]$ leading to first order dependence on $[H^+]$. Consequently, the plots of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ are found to be linear with a

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF REACTION RATE ON [PIPERIDONE]

$[H_2SO_4]=0.75 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Solvent : 80% HOAc– H_2O (v/v), Temp.=318 K, $[Tl^{III}]=2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu=2.25 M$

[Piperidone] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	k_{obs} $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	k_2 $\times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.5	2.26	1.51
2.0	3.15	1.58
2.5	3.77	1.51
3.0	4.63	1.54

positive slope and a zero intercept (Table 2). This clearly proves that in the absence of mineral acid the reaction is not feasible. A change in ionic strength shows no pronounced effect. Increase in the acetic acid content of the medium increases the rate of oxidation. The values of $10^4 k_{obs} (\text{s}^{-1})$ in 60, 70, 75, 80 and aqueous 90% (v/v) acetic acid are respectively 2.11, 2.35, 2.65, 3.15 and 7.38 for 3-methyl. The present investigation is interesting in that an inflex in the rate is observed at 90% AcOH in all the six 4-piperidones. Hence the

TABLE 2—ACID DEPENDENCE ON REACTION RATE

$[Tl^{III}]=2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp =318 K, Solvent : 80% HOAc– H_2O (v/v)

$[H_2SO_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	k_{obs} $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_{obs} \times 10^4$ $[H^+]$ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.5	2.27	2.27
0.75	3.15	2.1
1.0	4.00	2.0
1.25	4.9	1.98

reaction is strongly dielectric dependent confirming that the participation of a positive ion $Tl(OAc)_2^+$ and a dipole molecule piperidone in the rate-determining step in the present study. Henry³ also reported $Tl(OAc)_2^+$ to be the most active electrophilic species in aqueous acetic acid,

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIOUS SUBSTITUENTS ON REACTION RATE

[Tl^{III}]= 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [Piperidone]= 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄]=0.75 mol dm⁻³, Solvent : 80% HOAc-H₂O (v/v), Temp.=318 K, $\mu=2.25$ M

Piperidone	$k_a \times 10^3$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
3,5-Dimethyl	0.0767	82.5	97.0	79.0	-49.7
3-H	1.26	113.4	95.7	110.8	47.5
8-Methyl	1.58	112.0	95.1	109.4	45.0
3-Ethyl	1.97	100.0	94.5	97.4	9.1
3-Isopropyl	2.49	100.2	93.9	97.6	11.6
3,3-Dimethyl	2.79	96.0	93.6	93.4	-0.6

The reactions have been studied at four different temperatures and from the temperature dependence of k_{obs} , the values of E_a , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger have been computed (Table 3). The constancy in ΔG^\ddagger values indicates that the same mechanism is operative in all the six piperidones.

Substituent effect: The substituted 1-hetero-4-cyclohexanols have been shown to exist in anchored chair conformation with alkyl and phenyl groups in the most stable equatorial position³. The same can be expected in 3-alkyl-1-hetero-4-piperidones. An interesting observation in the oxidation rates is the effect of alkyl group adjacent to the reaction centre. The increased strain in the ring due to the vicinal alkyl substituent as a result of non-bonded steric interaction is relieved during oxidation thereby enhancing the rate of oxidation. Therefore, 3-alkyl substituted 4-piperidones react at a faster rate than the corresponding 2,6-diphenyl-4-piperidones. A comparison of the rate constants for the Tl^{III} oxidation of 4-piperidones indicates that 3-alkyl substituent enhances the rate of oxidation; larger the size of the substituent greater is the oxidation rate which falls in the order, 3,3-dimethyl > 3-isopropyl > 3-ethyl > 3-methyl > 3-H > 3,5-dimethyl (Table 3). The higher rate constant of 3,3-dimethyl may be due to increased gauche interactions. The least reactivity of 3,5-dimethyl is attributed to non-chair conformation in which the non-bonded steric interactions have been alleviated to a large extent⁴ restricting the oxidation to the first stage of formation of 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenyl-5-hydroxypiperidin-4-one which is supported by the stoichiometry 1 : 1.

Mechanism: The enolic form which contains a double bond can react with Tl^{III} acetate forming organometallic derivative with more facility like olefins⁵. Formation of enol is however not a rate-determining step as the observed rate is not independent of Tl^{III}. Tl^{III} acetate essentially behaves as a two-electron oxidant and the experimental results show that each α -C-H bond ruptures by a two-electron transfer. Therefore the oxidation of 4-piperidones in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of sulphuric acid may be interpreted by invoking

oxythallation of the enol form followed by dethallation. The proposed mechanism (Scheme 1) finds support from the fact that stable oxythallation adducts of the type H-O-C-C-Tl(OAc)₂ have actually been isolated in the oxidation of olefins⁶ in aqueous acetic acid. Tl^{III} oxidation of alkenols in aqueous perchloric acid also shows the formation of oxythallation adduct⁶. These facts reveal that the oxidation of 4-piperidones through enol form would involve carbon-thallium bond formation. Organothallium derivatives are known to be unstable to solvolysis and decompose easily to give a diketone as the final product. A similar mechanism has also been envisaged for the Tl^{III} oxidation of 4-piperidones studied by us.

Experimental

Thallium(III) acetate has been prepared from thallic oxide (B.D.H.). 4-Piperidones have been prepared as per the literature⁷. Acetic acid (analaR) unaffected by chromic acid was used. The reaction was followed under pseudo-first order condition by estimating the rate of disappearance of Tl^{III} by iodometry. Experiments were conducted in 80% acetic acid (v/v) at constant [H⁺] and ionic strength, $\mu=2.25$ M, sulphuric acid being the source of H⁺. The acid concentration was varied from 0.5 to 1.25 M. H₂SO₄, less than 0.5 M, was not sufficient for complete liberation of iodine and to give a sharp end-point and more than 1.25 M caused the separation of piperidone as piperidonehydrogensulphate. The concentrations of substrate used were 1.5, 2, 2.5 and 3×10^{-3} M. The solubility problem did not permit to go higher than 3×10^{-3} M. The concentration lower than 1.5×10^{-3} M slowed down the reaction rate to a very large extent. The stoichiometry can be expressed by the equations as shown in Chart 1. The products were identified by tlc, ir and nmr spectral data and qualitative tests. The main product isolated in the reaction mixture was a diketone which was characterised by the formation of the corresponding coloured inner complex nickeldioxime salts⁸ and by the corresponding 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

3-alkyl - 2,6 - diphenyl piperidin - 4,5 - dione

Scheme 1

Chart 1

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